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Exploring the Lived Experiences of Secondary Out-of-the-Field Social Science Teachers in Teaching Different Subject Areas

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Abstract

This qualitative study focused on the lived experiences of secondary social science out-of-the-field teachers which become a concern since it has an impact on the quality of education. The theory of Vygotsky (1978), social constructivism, and Shulman's (1986) Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Subject Matter Knowledge (SMK) are utilized to anchor this study. This study employs a qualitative research methodology, namely a hermeneutic method of research. The data were acquired from five (5) participants from the Schools Division of Quezon City who were chosen using a purposive sampling technique and employed a thematic analysis to reveal the experience of the participants. The findings revealed that the inadequate number of teachers is a primary reason for teaching outside their specialization. Despite initial apprehension, these teachers demonstrate adaptability and confidence in their assigned subjects. They prioritize effective learning through creative teaching methods and interactive activities. However, teaching unfamiliar subjects presents challenges due to limited content knowledge and an unfamiliar environment. Despite this, the teachers show resilience by utilizing various learning materials, seeking help from colleagues, and planning lessons meticulously. Colleague support plays a crucial role in aiding these teachers, providing guidance, resources, and moral support.

Keywords: *out-of-the-field-teacher, subject area, social science teacher, resiliency, lived experiences*

Introduction

To be an effective teacher requires mastery of the subject and pedagogical content as well as the ability to apply it in classroom settings (Jeschke et al., 2021). Hence the teacher's expertise in the subject is significant to effective learning. However, some teachers are instructing in subjects outside their specialization, referred to as "Out of the Field Teachers". According to Co et al (2021), out-of-the-field teachers are teaching outside of their expertise in a situation where educators are tasked with teaching subjects they lack sufficient training and qualifications. In addition, Lopez and Roble (2022) noted that out-of-the-field teachers are certified teachers who become unqualified due to teaching non-specialized courses, and this unqualified teacher might have a negative impact on the quality of education as well as the well-being of the teachers.

Teaching outside of the area of expertise not only causes uncertainty in the subject and can influence student engagement and learning outcomes, but teachers often become less confident, resulting in inefficient teaching (Caldis, 2019). In the Philippines, Out-of-field teaching is an essential but long-unrecognized issue in schools and the Department of Education. This may be due to the department's long-standing practice of using out-of-the-field teaching as a last resort to cover teaching vacancies and the fact that no reforms have been implemented to date to address issues regarding out-of-the-field teaching in DepEd schools across the nation. Furthermore, the country's adoption of the K-12 curriculum has created a huge demand for qualified teachers in specialized fields (Baez - Hernandez, 2019); hence, some teachers are assigned to teach subjects they need to be more specialized in.

With the implementation of Republic Act No. 9155, the "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001" in the Philippines, the nation supports neighborhood projects aimed at enhancing educational facilities and the United Nations' goal to provide quality education as a key to the world's sustainable development. Hence the issue of out-of-the-field teaching is one of the hindrances to quality education. Furthermore, there is little research that particularly examines the lived experiences of social science instructors teaching various courses in public secondary schools, and there are few studies of out-of-the-field teachers in the Philippines' metropolitan areas. Consequently, the researchers aimed to address these study gaps.

Research Questions

The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of secondary social science teachers in teaching different subject areas at public secondary schools in Quezon City. At this research stage, out-of-the-field teaching is defined as teaching other subjects such as TLE, MAPEh, Filipino, and other subjects by a teacher who specializes in social science. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of Social Science out-of-the-field secondary teachers?
2. What strategies do Social Science out-of-the-field secondary teachers employ to overcome the challenges of teaching other subjects?
3. How do Social Science out-of-the-field secondary Teachers, provide valuable insights into teaching other subjects?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to understand the realities and challenges encountered by secondary school social science teachers when teaching subjects outside their specialized field. It used a qualitative research hermeneutic phenomenology research design to answer the problem statement on the lived experience of secondary social science out-of-the-field teachers. According to Tenny et al. (2022), qualitative research is a sort of study that delves deeper into real-world situations by gathering participant experiences, perceptions, and behaviors.

This hermeneutic phenomenology was used to explore the lived experience of out-of-the-field social science teachers, their coping strategies, and insights into the phenomenon. Using a hermeneutic phenomenological research approach, the research explored the underlying meanings, perceptions, and interpretations inherent in the daily experiences of these teachers by examining their unique journeys, struggles, and potential coping strategies within the educational context. According to Sloan and Bowe (2014), hermeneutic phenomenology recommends the researcher interpret the meaning found in phenomena. The emphasis is on comprehending the meaning of experience by seeking themes and engaging with the facts interpretively, rather than on the essences that are significant in descriptive phenomenology. This approach appears to be most appropriate to describe the lived experiences of the Social Science teacher teaching subjects outside their specialization.

Participants

In this phenomenological study, five (5) Grade 7-10 public school teachers were selected based on the criteria. The participants must be currently teaching junior high school students in a public school for more than three years under the teaching category of Teacher I, II, or III. Additionally, the participants must specialize in Social Science but actively teach different subject area/s and have the willingness to participate in the study.

Instruments

The Researcher used three different methods in gathering needed data in accordance to achieve the objectives of the study such as interviews, observation, and documents.

Interview. A semi-structured interview, also known as a hybrid interview is a combination of an unstructured interview and a structured interview which allows new ideas to be brought up during the interview. A combination of closed- and open-ended questions are used in semi-structured interviews, frequently with additional why or how inquiries (Adams, 2015).

Observation. This form of data collecting allows the researcher to have a deeper understanding of the processes, culture, or individuals being studied. In qualitative research, observation is "one of the oldest and most fundamental research methodologies approaches." This method comprises systematic and appropriate data collecting using one's senses, notably gazing and hearing." (McKechnie, 2008).

Document Analysis. Document analysis is one useful technique that is commonly applied in qualitative research is document analysis. Analyzing a variety of documents, such as novels, newspaper stories, academic journal articles, and institutional reports, is what this involves. Any text-based document can serve as a source for qualitative analysis (Patton, 2014).

Procedure

Pre-interviews were undertaken to obtain interview consent and the participant's preferred time for the interview. To ensure the participant's comfort throughout the interview, the researcher introduced herself and mentioned the study's purpose before the interview began. To protect participant identification while still revealing background information, participant pseudonyms were used in the transcripts (see Table 1 Participant Demographic Data).

The interviews were recorded and transcribed within 24 hours of being done. Additionally, the participants' social and historical settings were considered. The Researcher regularly reflects on the questions asked during the interviews and the replies supplied by the participants during the analysis phase to avoid creating inappropriate analyses that would not achieve the study's objectives.

Participants' body language and other forms of semiosis as a mode of speech were also observed during the interview. Their nonverbal clues and interaction dynamics, which add to the overall context of the interview, were also examined. Furthermore, participants were asked to submit teaching loads, instructor assignments, and other documents that can be used in the study. The materials were studied by identifying various themes, concepts, and codes relevant to the study.

Data Analysis

After the Researcher collected data through the process of conducting purposive interviews and then transcribed the discussions verbatim, the data were analyzed using the seven steps Modified van Kaam approach laid out by Moustakas 1994. The seven steps are the following:

Horizontalization

Horizontalization is the process of noting and categorizing noteworthy participant responses by reading and rereading the verbatim transcription (Buenacosa & Patella, 2022). In this study, all data were processed equally, and pertinent information, such as words, phrases, sentences, or emotional responses, were listed. In this step, the researcher put all of her previous notions about the subject on hold.

Reduction and Elimination

This process determined the invariant constituents by reducing and removing irrelevant data. In this study, the researcher excluded irrelevant data while retaining relevant data about the phenomenon. She determined whether the data were relevant to the social science out-of-the-field lived experiences and whether the data could be reduced to its latent meaning. Furthermore, material that appeared to overlap, repeat, or ambiguous was removed.

Clustering and Thematizing

In this study, the thematic categories were formed by grouping invariant parts that were related to one another. These thematic categories that emerged from the analysis were the fundamental themes of the data that reflect the participants' common perceptions and experiences.

Validation

This stage establishes whether or not the themes and invariant elements are correct. The Researcher determined whether the invariant elements and themes were expressed explicitly and were compatible in the transcript; otherwise, the data had been removed. The validation was carried out initially by the researcher. The Researcher's adviser also authenticated the transcripts and ran the audit trail. This external auditor also provided comments and suggestions for improving the themes.

Individual Textual Description

Textural descriptions were constructed to describe the individual experiences of the participants. In this study, the description was constructed using the relevant, validated invariant constituents and themes as well as verbatim examples from the transcription.

Individual Structural Description

This step necessitates an imaginative variation to contextualize the phenomenon's experience when the primary interpretation of facts comes into play. As a result, the participants in this study have their structural description. These descriptions were based on the participants' firsthand knowledge of the phenomenon.

Textural-Structural Description

This process is also known as Synthesis. This is where researchers begin to combine textual and structural information to provide a thorough explanation of the phenomenon. This is what distills the phenomenon's lived experience. In this final stage of this study, a detailed transcript that included all of the themes was created. These themes constitute the analysis's conclusion, which addresses the study's aim. The textural and structural descriptions were combined into themes in this study, and the participants' experiences were presented.

Essence

The Researcher created a combination of structural and textual descriptions. A description conveys the core of the phenomenon. The primary focus of this is on participants shared common experiences in the study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in qualitative research, as outlined by Mirza et al., (2023), encompass pivotal principles guiding research endeavors. These principles revolve around the fundamental treatment of all participants with respect and trust, acknowledging and accommodating diverse factors such as age, sex, race, religion, political beliefs, and lifestyle.

The Researcher established transparent and open relationships with participants across various phases of the study while diligently seeking voluntary informed consent before any data collection. Anonymity and data privacy remain paramount, demanding careful measures to safeguard participants' identities and information. Continuous communication regarding the research's progress with participants and the provision of their responses or transcripts post-data collection are established. Moreover, this study upholds trustworthiness through valid, reliable, and credible practices form the cornerstone of ethical qualitative research.

Results and Discussion

Operational Data Collection

The data were gathered from various schools in Quezon City. A face-to-face semi-structured interview was done with each participant

to get insight into their experiences as social science out-of-field teachers. The Researcher interviewed the participants according to their availability, some interviews are done in the evening for their convenience. An interview guide questionnaire was utilized to get meaningful data from the participants using their own words. Individual interviews were conducted with the participants to acquire a full grasp of their experience as social science out-of-field teachers. A qualitative interview was used, with open-ended and follow-up questions that allowed participants to engage more by answering questions in their own words. Most of the interviews lasted for more than twenty minutes and participants showed their enthusiasm in answering the questions. During the interview, the Researcher also took notes of important information and nonverbal cues that the participants showed. To ensure the recording's reliability, the interview was audio and video recorded with the participants' permission using the researcher's phone and laptop.

Operational Data Analysis

Phenomenological data analysis grasps and enlightens a phenomenon's meaning, formation, and essential nature through lived experience (Patton, 2014) The data in this study were analyzed using the following procedures: setting aside personal judgment, phenomenological reduction (bracketing, horizontalization, clustering themes, textural description of experience), imaginative variations (structural description of experience), and textural-structural synthesis (Moustakas, 1994).

Before delving into the data analysis, the researcher disregarded her preconceived notions and opinions regarding the participant's experiences. Throughout the study, she took reflective notes to avoid drawing parallels between the data provided by the participants and her own experience teaching social science.

Phenomenological reduction was then utilized. The Researcher employed textural experience description, clustering themes, bracketing, and horizontalization. After the interview was transcribed, a comprehensive analysis of the data was initiated. The Researcher went over the transcriptions several times to find noteworthy statements that would allow the triangulated data to be horizontalized and reveal the significance of the participants' efforts. The themes that were classified were identified by going over the interview again, underlining the statements, and making side notes. Statements were grouped into topics after being coded. Textural analysis was used to determine the whatness of the teachers' life experiences or endeavors.

The Researcher attempted to comprehend the structural essence of the phenomenon by exploring the imaginative variation that followed. The research in this study explored “how” secondary social science teachers experience teaching outside their specialization to uncover the significant meaning of these experiences. In the last stage, textural-structural analysis was employed to unify the significant experiences of social science out-of-the-field teachers regarding their lived experiences and resiliency in teaching outside their specialization.

Participants' Demographic Profile

The five (5) participants in this study were drawn from various schools in the division of Quezon City and selected through purposeful criterion sampling. All participants were regular-permanent public-junior high school teachers, who teach subjects that are outside their subject specialization such as Filipino, MAPEh, and ESP. Pseudonyms were used to assure anonymity among participants and to protect the integrity of the school where they taught, only the name of the division was provided.

Table 1. *Participants' Demographic Data*

Name*	Sex	Age	Years of Teaching Experience	Grade Level	Subject Teaching	Teaching Position
Kristian	Male	-	19	Grade 10	Filipino	Teacher I
JP	Male	30 years old	6	Grade 10	MAPEh	Teacher II
Macky	Male	27 years old	6	Grade 8	MAPEh	Teacher I
Christian	Male	26 years old	6	Grade 7	MAPEh	Teacher I
Arra	Female	29 years old	5	Grade	ESP	Teacher I

*Pseudonyms

Participant 1, Kristian

Kristian obtained his degree from Ligao Community College in Ligao Albay. He has been a teacher for nineteen years. He taught English and Araling Panlipunan in a private school. When he started attending Bicol's public schools, he was given teaching assignments in a variety of disciplines, including Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health, English, and Araling Panlipunan. After relocating to Quezon City, he was given a teaching assignment at San Francisco High School, where he has been teaching Filipino to Grade 10 students for over five years. Christian enjoys his teaching career since he has a positive attitude toward life.

Participant 2, JP

JP graduated with his bachelor's degree in Secondary Education majoring in Social Science at National Teachers College and is currently enrolled in a Master's Degree in Education majoring in Social Science at the University of the Philippines, Diliman. As he entered public school, his journey was not that easy, he became an excess Araling Panlipunan teacher at Sergio Osmena High School and moved to San Francisco High School as a teacher where he taught Entrepreneurship subject in senior high school for almost a year. As he regresses to his original school designation, he is instructed to teach Araling Panlipunan 8 and Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health 10. Despite having a different working environment, he adjusts easily as he continues to have a good relationship with his

colleagues.

Participant 3, Macky

Macky was advised to teach Humanities and Social Sciences as his key subjects during his senior high school private teaching experience. Today Macky is assigned to Pugad Lawin High School as a Grade 8 MAPEh teacher. In 2017, he graduated from New Era University with a bachelor's degree in secondary teaching with a social science concentration. He is currently enrolled in National Teachers College to pursue a master's degree in education major social science. Regarding his teaching style, he identified himself as an authoritarian and a disciplinary educator as he believes that respect fosters learning.

Participant 4, Christian

Christian received magna cum laude diploma for his bachelor's degree in secondary education majoring in social science from Metro Manila College, where he is also currently enrolled in the same institution and already working on his thesis writing. He currently works as a Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan coordinator and teaches Grade 7 MAPEh and Araling Panpinunan subjects at Dona Rosario High School. He is one of the Carl Balita Review Center's nationwide lecturers for teacher licensure exams. In terms of his career, Christian is not afraid to take chances; while he waits for his appointment at the public school, he even started working as a call center agent in a BPO company. Given that he puts his all into his teaching, he describes himself as a devoted educator. He considers education as the greatest equalizer in society.

Participant 5, Arra

Arra graduated from New Era University with a bachelor of education major in social science, and she continues her competence in the field as she is currently enrolled in a master's degree at the same institution. When she decided to be a public school teacher, she made a tough decision to apply at the elementary level for she experienced an unpleasant encounter teaching high school students. She taught all subjects to her Grade 2 students during her elementary teaching. However, Arra's eagerness to teach social science subjects drives her to go back to teaching secondary level. Today she is connected in Pugad Lawin High School and teaching ESP or Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao. She has that bubbly personality that she also applies in her teaching.

Discussion, Presentation, and Interpretation

The discussion, presentation, and interpretation are relevant to the statement of the problem of the study that was answered by five (5) secondary social science out-of-the-field teacher participants. Moreover, their answers were incorporated and given a theme and category. The study generated six (6) themes, 18 categories, and 100 different codes.

The Lived Experiences of Social Science Out-of-the-Field Teachers

The secondary social science out-of-the-field teachers experience changes in their teaching career as they are assigned a subject that they are not familiar with. Effective teaching might face substantial obstacles when one is teaching subjects outside of one's area of expertise. As a result, a major theme emerging from this research study is the lived experiences and challenges faced by secondary school teachers who are assigned to teach social science courses outside of their areas of specialization.

Theme 1: Adaptation Amidst Adversity

Secondary teachers specialize in a particular subject to provide students with in-depth information, However, there are still hired public secondary teachers who are assigned outside their specialization. These circumstances reflect the character of a teacher in times of difficulty. The study revealed categories from this theme including anticipation, inadequate numbers of teachers, and confidence.

Category 1: Anticipation. The social science teachers geared themselves for the possibility of uncontrollable conditions once they started teaching in a public school. Given that some of them had experience teaching other subjects before attending the public school system and that others were aware of similar concerns, they were prepared for the concept of teaching subjects other than their areas of expertise.

For instance, Participant 1, Kristian, "Yeah Expected ko na talaga Kasi ako for once sa probinsya ko kilala ako ng Deped" L7, in addition Participant 2, JP may narinig na rin akong ganung stories. Inexpect kong ibibigay sakin values education" L4-L5, similarly Participant 4, Christian, "nung time na nag apply ako ,ready naman na ko na makapagturo ako ng ibang subject and yun nga yun na nillook forward ko ni reready ko na yung sarili ko." L4-L6.

In the study of Torcino and Villocino (2023), the widespread problem of non-specialized teachers is universal. Teachers assigned to subjects outside their specialization is inevitable, and every type of school, whether it's private or public, religious or secular, rural or urban, face the same issue. As teachers, we need to recognize the nature of our profession. It's crucial to acknowledge that unexpected situations may arise, and we must remain receptive to potential career prospects.

Category 2, Inadequate number of teachers. The participants are excess teachers from the Araling Panlipunan Department since another department has a shortage of teachers, the social science teachers are assigned to other subjects to complete their teaching load.

Participant 1 Kristian, "reason kaya kinuha ako na magturo ng Filipino dahil kulang talaga sila ng Filipino teacher." L10,L11, in Belmonte et al.

addition Participant 3, Macky, “primary reason lang naman sakin is kulang sila sa MAPEH Sobra na yung AP teacher nila that time.” L4-L6. Similarly Participant 4, Christian, “ excess AP so binigyan ako ng limang MAPEH, dalawang AP lang yun yung binigay sakin” L1-L12.

In the study Co et. al. (2021) revealed that inequalities in teacher numbers and concerns about excess or deficiency of competent educators in a certain subject are the root causes of this out-of-field instruction. This concern about the number of teachers can also result in other problems in the education system such as concern about actual class size, teachers burnout, and overall quality of education.

Category 3, Confidence. The majority of social science participants showed confidence in their competence to teach various subjects as they already had a prior understanding of the subjects assigned to them.

for instance, Participant 4, Christian, “Kahit among subject po willing po ako ,siyempre ganun naman lahat diba pag nag aapply, lahat willing eh , lahat kaya mong gawin , sabi ko “yes po”.Nung tinanong ako nun hinanda ko na sarili ko na ah magtuturo ako ng ibang subject. Nung na in na ko pag papasok ko”L8-L11

The participant accepted the duty with assurance given the fact that they have familiarity with the subject matter they were assigned. This prior exposure provided them with a solid foundation from which to navigate the challenges of teaching outside their specialization.

Participant 1, Kristian, “hindi ako actually parang naging apprehensive parang ahm ok lang din sa part ko kasi nung nagtuturo din ako ng english na enjoy ko siya”L16,L17 also Participants 2, JP, “No pressure naman kasi MAPEH may mga content siya na align naman sa Social Studies “L10,L11

Despite these challenges to content knowledge, teachers accept teaching outside their specialization for as long as they continue their profession (Tingzon & Buyok, 2022). This challenge for out-of-the-field social science teachers will allow them to learn, adapt, be emotionally ready, and be open to learning experiences.

Theme 2: Effective Learning through Innovative Teaching

Teaching outside their specialization doesn't hinder social science teachers from having effective learning for their students. The participants revealed the utilization of different teaching strategies that engage students in critical thinking and facilitate a deeper understanding of concepts. Two categories arise from this theme, interactive teaching and learning and interdisciplinary teaching.

Category 1, Interactive Teaching. The majority of out-of-field social science teachers expressed confidence in the effectiveness of student learning.

As emphasized by Participant 1, Kristian, “Definitely, yung assessment ko sa mga bata dun ko makikita kung may learning talaga sa mga bata. Kung na attain nila yung objective na hinihingi ng lesson. Yes effective, I believe effective” L24-L25 additionally Participant 2, JP, “I guess kasi mas engaging yung approach ko eh very ano yung ginagamit kong strategy sa kanila kagaya din sa social studies, group woks talaga kumbaga yung learning very interactive. “L16-L18

The participant used various techniques of assessment to see whether student learning was present in the classroom. The interactive methods of instruction used by the participants make the educational process more collaborative and allow students to engage with one another in meaningful ways. These interactive exercises were useful tools for creating student-centered learning environments in which students could actively engage with course material, connect with their classmates, and build their grasp of subjects.

For instance Participant 1, Kristian, “dami nating strategy na ginagamit na mas ano mas ano ang mga bata interactive yung dating sa kanila like for example minsan kung may mga halimbawa sa grade 10 ang topic ay kontemporaryong isyu so minsan gagamit ka ng debate sa klase para mapalabas mo yung opinyon ng mga bata yung kaalaman nila yung concept nila kung tama ma. Kung baga yung makes the room come alive in all the strategies you are using”L30-L34, ahm nag iincorporate din ako ng theater mga ah ano pa ba minsan may mga pa drama drama pa ko na pageant pageant sar room or parang mini tour meron pa kong mga activity na ah yung pangarang nangingisda sila ng concept dun sa fishball para lang buhay yung klase para nag eenjoy sila while learning”L37-L40 in addition Participant 4, Christian, “ Pero ngayon kasi na mamana ko na mag integrate ng ibat ibang activities, mag integrate ng ibat ibang ah tawag dito methodology sa pagtuturo ahmm kunwari mag papagawa ka ng mga collaborative work ,performance based assesment, may mga ganun na ko ngayon eh ,dati hindi puro paper and pencil lang tapos lecture parang ganun lang , ngayon hindi , varied na yung strategies na ina apply ko , may constructivist na so, yun yung meron.” L43-,L48. Furthermore, Participant 5 , Arra, “ Nag papareporting din ako , pero more on dramatization and role playing kasi dun parang naka characterize saka yung ano pa ngayon na aadopt ng mga bata yung values so paano nila yung eh ano tawag dito , isasabuhay yun.”L33-L36

According to Co et al. (2021), teachers teaching outside their specialization is crucial for effective teaching and learning, therefore out-of-the-field teachers need to use classroom activities that engage student learning such as role-playing, reporting, the board works, group activities, and educational video presentation along with guided questions that can help for student mastery of subject matter. These different teaching strategies would assist teachers in dealing with their current situation and demonstrate their adaptability (Lagria, 2021). Furthermore, Torcino and Villocino (2023) revealed that teachers will acquire the skill of adaptability in their teaching

approaches, utilizing interactive teaching methods like hands-on activities and integrating games to both sustain children's engagement and facilitate learning.

Category 2, Interdisciplinary Teaching. Despite teaching outside their specialization, participants still instill their expertise in strategies and content in social science. Their knowledge of the social science disciplines allows their teaching to integrate social science into their lessons, resulting in interdisciplinary teaching. Participants revealed that they incorporate history, geography, culture, and society in their lessons integrating these disciplines in social science into their discussion creates more depth in the learning of the students.

As emphasized by Participant 1, Kristian, “Kasi being an Araling Panlipunan teacher ang dali mong maituro yung literature part ng Filipino and English. At kaya nga minsan may mga estudyante na nagtatanong sakín “Sir parang ang dami mong sagot sa mga katanungan namin parang lagi kang ready” ang sagot ko sa kanila Im social science major kasi so napapakinabangan ko yung pagiging social science major ko in teaching Filipino.” L17-L21, Participant 2, JP, “At some point yes nagagamit ko yung strategies saka and discipline sa socsci sa mapeh” L22, also Participant 3, Macky, “Yes absolutely nagagamit ko siya may mga certain topic talaga na sa MAPEH na natouch yung historical saka cultural for example ano sa grade 9 MAPEH may tinataackle kasi dun na history of Roman Period, History of Renaissance, So yung na tataackle talaga yung content knowledge ko from AP na History tapos dun sa MAPEH.” L23-L26. In addition Participant 4, Christian, “Expertise siguro unang una sa Culture, kasi diba tayo as a social studies major inclined tayo sa Society, sa Sociology, inclined tayo sa pagtuturo ng culture, Sa MAPEH kasi parang meron sa touch ng Soc Sci talaga, Kunwari sa Music, bago mo pag aralan yung music ng Cordillera aralin mo muna yung geography niya and part yun ng AP, yung geography, aralin mo ung background nila aralin mo dun yung mga epeko, yung hudhud, andun yung mga yun eh. So tawag dito nacoconnect mo siya dun, nagtuturo ka ng literature, tapos nababanga mo siya sa geography, nababanga mo siya sa history, kunwari ituturo mo yung Mindoro, Palawan, siyempre ituturo mo yung geography kung saan sila matatagpuan, kung ano mga bagay na meron sila. So yung content na expertise ko pagsating sa Soc Sci mabilis ko siya na rerelete sa MAPEH, so ganun yung nangyayari. L51, -L61. Lastly Participant 5, Arra, “kasi ang na instill sakín yung social science, so minsan parang nagiging history yung dating ng pagtuturo ng ESP nah parang nahahaluan ko ng pagaka history vibes ganun,” L22-L23.

Their passion for teaching various social science disciplines remains evident throughout their teaching career. This excitement serves both educators and students by encouraging them to expand their knowledge of the subject and allowing them to integrate teachings from different areas, building a larger understanding beyond individual disciplines.

Theme 3: Challenges of Out-of-the-Field Social Science Teacher

The participants faced different challenges in teaching subjects outside of their specialization, in this theme two categories were revealed the struggle with content knowledge and unfamiliarity in their new working setup.

Category 1, Struggles with content knowledge. The out-of-the-field social science primary concern is the need for more knowledge of the subject content.

For instance, Participant 1, Kristian, “Ang pinaka una kong concern to teach is yung content talaga L42, Also Participant 3, Macky, “Isa sa mga problem dun yung content saka skills kasi I notice na yung ibang MAPEH teachers may expertise talaga sa isang certain area” L33-L34. Furthermore Participant 5, Christian, “Problem ano yung content, kaya inalar ko siya” L63. Lastly Participant 5, Arra, yung content kasi kailangan ko siyang tawag dito kailangan ko siyang pababawin” L44, L45

This leads to apprehension about their ability to deliver the instruction to students properly.

As emphasized, Participant 1, Kristian lagi yung apprehension ko na you know baka mayroon na you bright student na lagi na eencounter ka na baka magkamali ka, at alam nilang mali ka so dun ako lagi apprehensive lagi. L42-L43 and Participant 5, Arra, na-encounter ko una nahahirapan ako na I deliver sa bata as is yung topic L488

Lopez and Roble (2022) revealed that good teaching requires at least three factors, knowledge content, pedagogical content knowledge, and teaching skills. Additionally primary challenge of teaching outside the specialization is the teachers' limited knowledge of the subject matter, teaching preparation becomes complicated for them, and implementing student activities becomes decisive (Co et al., 2021). This is in line with Du Plessis; (2013) statement that teachers who teach a subject they do not understand are concerned that the knowledge they share with students will not be sufficient to influence their future. Teachers in secondary schools are expected to have expertise not just in pedagogical teaching but also in content knowledge; this expertise in the content serves as a guide on the best teaching strategies to use in a certain lesson.

Category 2, Overwhelmed by Unfamiliarity. The social science out-of-the-field teacher experiences adjustment from the new working setup. The majority of the participants are overwhelmed with various amount of school activities such as coordinatorship, sports coaching, and school division competitions that they have to handle.

Specifically Participant 2, JP emphasized, “for example Music, Arts, Music and Health and daming components, Since MAPEH kasi very ah ang dami niya ding specialization, for example classical music ako eh hindi ako ganun fun ng classical music medyo struggling din sakín na magturo ng Music and hindi din ako kumakanta kaya kahit mag pa activity ako ng singing ayoko personally kasi hindi din ako kumakanta kaya medyo struggling din sakín yun kasi as parts of components din” L28-L32. In addition Participant 3, Macky, “Sa

Music magaling kumanta, magaling magbasa ng mga nota, Yung PE naman magagaling sumayaw magaling mag turo ng step yung chereography nung mga nao ginagamit nilang sayang, yung sa Arts yung mga painting ,drawing,sketching etc. yun ayun yung mga challenges na kapag may mga topic na need ng skills more on content or knowledge dun ako tagilid or alanganin.Siguro yung mga problem yung sport officiating kasi di ako ano eh more on sport person so inaaral ko pa talaga ng ilang beses bago ako mag undergo halimbawa ng mga volleyball ,basketball, kasi wala namang ganun sa AP.” L34,L35,,L36,L37,L38,L39,L40,L41. Lastly Participant 4, Christian, “ng tawag dito yung na ano ko masyadong maraming activities sobrang dami talaga so parang minsan na ooverwhelmed na kami kasi ang daming pinapagawa samin” L63-L65.

Coping with the Challenges Posed by Social Science Out-of-the-Field Teachers

As secondary social science out-of-the-field teachers face the challenges in teaching outside their specialization, their characteristics and qualities as teachers are revealed. Through the lens of these emergent themes, this study gains a deeper understanding of the resilience displayed by out-of-field teachers as they strive to meet the educational needs of their students despite the obstacles they face.

Theme 4: Resilience and Adaptability in Teaching

The study revealed the resiliency of the out-of-the-field social science teachers to cope with the challenges in their teaching careers. Regardless of the participants' lack of content knowledge in the subject matter, they continue to demonstrate their commitment to benefiting student learning. In this theme, three categories were exhibited, the secondary out-of-the-field teachers' preparedness, resourcefulness, and receptiveness.

Category 1, The participants revealed their preparedness. Before arriving at the class, they plan ahead of time, and, given their lack of experience in the subject, they exert an extra effort to study the lesson through reading, which allows them to have in-depth knowledge of the subject.

As emphasized Participant 1, Kristian, “The first step that i do ako mismo nag rereview sa sarili ko diba hindi ako haharap sa klase na hindi ako ready” L48-L51 in addition Participant 3, Macky, “ Siyempre yung una inaaral ko bago ko i deliver yung contents” L44. Furthermore, Participant 4, Christian , “ Ang ginagawa ko kasi ngayon ahead of time nag rerecord na ako , hindi ko na pinapaabot yung pag tapos ng exam dun na ko nag rerecord.” L104-L105

Pacana et al. (2019) found out that the challenges the out-of-the-field social science teachers face allow them to develop adaptability and resilience. These Filipino traits are coping mechanisms that are key to survival in any situation. Bugwak (2021) revealed that out-of-the-field teachers have their strengths and weaknesses and what matters is they continue learning, They devote themselves to professional growth which is essential to keep them updated on the trends and innovations in education.

Category 2 is receptiveness. The participants show their initiative to seek help from their colleagues in times when they need help in understanding a certain topic and they even ask for suggestions on what activities or teaching strategies are the best to utilize.

As stated Participant 1, Kristian, “So i think yung attitude ko na yun yung pagiging open ko sa pag katuto , you know kahit teacher ka kailangan mo parin matuto at hinihingi mo yung tulong na yun sa mga kasamahan mo I keep my mind open:” L,63-L65. Also Participant 3, Macky, “siyempre nag aask din talaga ako sa maga MAPEh teacher na talagang ilang years na nagtuturo, pano siya gawin, pano siya ituro saka yung the best way para ma execute yung particular topic or lesson.” L44-L46, In addition Participant 4, Christian , “ Saka yung pagtatanong sa ibang mga ka work ko , like yung coordinator namin sa MAPEh , pag di ko talaga alam didirecho ko dun “Sir paano ba to ituro? Sir pano yung ginawa ninyo dito? Parang ganun nangingi talaga ako ng tulong sa kanya kasi siya mas nakakaalam.”sir ganto ginawa namin”, “Sir ituturo ko pa ba tong part na to?” . Dahil dun na guguiide din siguro ako “L118-122. Furthermore, Participant 5, Arra, “Nagtatanong ako sa aking head teacher , sa ibang co teacher ko sa ESP , kung paano ituturo yun, kung paano I dedeliver yun.” L50-L51

Their characteristic of being receptive to feedback and asking for help from other experienced teachers in a specific subject are some coping strategies of out-of-the-field teachers (Bugwak, 2021).

Category 3, resourcefulness. The out-of-the-field social science teachers demonstrate their resourcefulness by having in-depth knowledge of the subject content. The participants revealed their effort to look for different learning materials that they could use to deliver the lesson properly to the student and they textbooks, division modules, and technological platforms such as Google and YouTube.

For instance Participant 1, Kristian, “everytime kasi na may topic may lesson i make it a point na talagang mag bubuklat ako ng libro at machecheck ako sa google mas sisikapin ko na aralin yun” L68- L71. In addition Participant 3, Macky,“siguro siyempre dun narin papasok yung pagiging researcher ng teacher, syempre mag reresearch siya about dun sa topic bago niya i discuss.” L47,L48

Furthermore, Participant 4, Christian, “, ang ginawa ko talaga nanuod ako ng mga lectures ng youtube, malaking tulong ng youtube kasi na si- simplify nila yung mga information saka tinuturo at the same time mero”n na silang format kung paano siya ituturo , yung flow ,so malaking tulong din yun. Tapos basa talaga basa basa basa , ano ba yung mga dapat ko pang eh ituro and yung module din na binigay ng division mas simple mas mabilis ko siyang naiintidihan” L112,-L118

In the findings of Torcino and Villocino (2023), out-of-the-field teachers showed their resourcefulness in learning materials by watching video lessons, as well as their effort to have extra time to read books, research teaching strategies, and look for more resources just to give quality education to their students. It is given that teachers are already well experienced in researching reliable learning resources that will guide them in the teaching process, however, these out-of-the-field teachers exert extra time and effort to become resources as they face the challenges in the content knowledge.

Theme 5: Encouraging Professional Network

The participants' positive working environment improve their engagement in teaching subjects outside their specialization. Two categories emerged from this theme including commendable and colleague support.

Category 1 is commendable. The never-ending effort of the out-of-the-field social science teachers is greatly appreciated by their head department. The majority of participants receive positive feedback from their head department to the point where their head department wants them to stay with the subject they are teaching. This can be seen in the participant's response.

Participant 3, Macky, "so far natutuwa naman siya , minsan nga sinasabi nila na mag mapeh na lang daw ako all throughout wag na daw akong bumalik ng AP kasi nga natutuwa sila sa way ng teaching ko na parang kakaiba na hindi nila nakita before sa ibang MAPEh teacher." L51-L53. In addition Participant 4, Christian, "Sa feedback naman ng head ko goods naman,siyempre nakikita naman niya yung effort ko sa pag aaral ng content, sabi niya nga parang ayaw na daw niya akong tanggalin sa MAPEh ganun" L124-L126. Moreover, Participant 5 , Arra," ang feedback sakin parang matagal na ako ESP teacher kasi parang nakuha ko na kung paano makukuha yung attensyon ng mga bata pag nagtuturo ng ESP." L501-L502.

Category 2, colleague support. They are always willing to answer their inquiries, offer guidance on teaching strategies and help them to navigate the unfamiliarity of the subject.

For instance Participant 1, Kristian, "yung mga kasamahan ko kasi naiimbsan yung worry ko kasi hindi naman ako napapdala sa mga workshop atleast yung mga colleagues ko nakakulong para sila nayung tumulong sakin na kapag mayroon akong katanungan sila na ang magbibigay sakin ng kasagutan" L60-L63. In addition Participant 2, JP, "may co- teacher akong teaching for 5 years so guided naman niya ko sa pagtuturo sa MAPEH" L49. Lastly Participant 4, Christian, "meron kaming tinatawag na team teaching ,magtutulungan kami ng meron kasi kaming coordinator dun , siya lang ang nag iisang MAPEh major dun the rest ng ahat ng teacher dun ibang major na, Hindi madami kami as in isa lang talaga yung original na MAPEh, then the rest hugot nalang . Yun tapos ginagawa namin team teaching" L88-L93.

Fatima et al. (2020) revealed the significance of the good and positive relationships between principals and teachers that substantially impact student learning. When teachers are inspired and motivated in their responsibilities, it improves the educational experience. The coordinated work of principals and teachers is critical in molding kids' personalities and interactions with peers and classmates. Additionally, Pacana et al. (2019) reveals the importance of having harmonious relationships between out-of-the-field teachers with their colleagues, specifically seasoned and expert teachers who can help them whenever they are confused or need assistance in teaching different subjects. They can ask relevant questions that can give them additional information which they can use for a better understanding of the subject. This correction and feedback from other teachers help them to become aware of their strengths and weaknesses (Tingzon & Buyok,2022) which guides them to enhance their skills and grow professionally (Spring & Hunter,2022)

Insights of Social Science Out-of-the-Field Teachers

Secondary social science teachers get important insights into their experiences as they work through the difficulties that come with instructing subjects outside of their area of expertise. This study provides a fundamental theme that emerges from these discussions, providing participants with a greater understanding of the nuances and complexities of teaching subjects they are unfamiliar with.

Theme 6: Fulfillment through Commitment

The participants stressed their passion and dedication, demonstrating their commitment to their profession. It revealed their sense of surprise and fulfillment in achieving success in areas they did not expect to excel in initially. In this theme, four categories emerge including dedication and passion in teaching, teaching satisfaction, depth in the subject matter, and maximizing teachers' continued learning.

Category 1, dedication and passion for teaching. The out-of-the-field social science teachers continually demonstrate their love for teaching. In times of difficulties they always look back on the core reasoning why they are teaching. This is shown in the participant's response.

As stated Participant 1 Kristian, " i strongly believe na when you are a teacher your really have a heart of a teacher not just the mind and if you have both the heart and the mind of a teacher thats you parang hindi siya dagdag na trabaho hindi siya kapaguran hindi siya yung tipong nalalamangan ka ng katrabaho mo bagkos parang yun yung pagkatao,you are born to do it , and you do it you know something noble for the youth" L88-L92. Additionally Participant 4, Christian, "kung titingnan mo lang din yung pagod, kung titingnan mo lang din yung sahod mapapagod at mapapagod ka talaga eh . Pero kung una titingnan mo yung para kanino mo ba ginagawa yan? Para sa estudyante mo. Dun ma rerealize mo , ah sayang naman yung pinapasok nila araw araw kung wala silang natutunan sayo."

L151-L155.

They are teaching and their love for their students is the reason they continue their profession. This is shown in the participant's response.

Participant 3, Macky, “Paano mo ihahandle yung mga problems , papabayaan mo ba sila or i address mo agad yung misbehavior na akita mo, kasi malaking factor nun eh parang pag for example misbehavior pag di mo pinansin yung ginawa ng bata na misconduct or hindi maganda sa classroom iisipin niya na gagawin niya yun in other day,” L73-L77. In addition Participant 4, Christian “ minsan sa pangangailangan lang talaga, at isipin mo kung wala ka don sino magtuturo sa mga bata, Oo yung nga yung goal natin eh, para sa bata,para sa bayan .” L175-L176. Furthermore, Participant 5, Arra, “ibigay nalang yung best yung ganun para ma provide yung necessary learnings ng mga bata” L76-L77.

Category 2, teaching satisfaction. They found satisfaction in their students' well-being, and witnessing their students' development gives them fulfillment as teachers. The success of their students is also the accomplishment of out-of-the-field social science teachers. Finding out that their students are doing well in their lives, winning different competitions, and seeing that they apply what they have learned, motivates out-of-the-field teachers to strive more and continue their teaching profession.

As emphasized, Participant 1, Kristian, “ diba masarap isipin na dumadaan sayo yung mga bata tapos nakikita mo yung development nila yung pag grow nila and eventually they will live their own lives ang pinaka maganda dun kapag nabalitaan mo yung estudyante mo is doing yung tinatawag na service to community at walang katumbas na halaga.” L92-L95. Additionally Participant 3, Macky, “yung di ko enexpect na parang nagechachampion yung hawak ko sa MAPEH kasi syempre hindi ako more on talaga eh. I mean first of all hindi talaga align yung knowledge ko sa MAPEh pero since napag aaralan naman siya at natutuwa ako sa mga output ng mga bata and feedback” L55-L58. Furthermore, Participant 4, Christian, “iba parin talaga pag passion mo yung pagtuturo eh, dun ka masaya saka kapag nakikita mo yung mga bata na masaya sayo at sila ay na momotivate mo , yun yung self fulfillment na tinatawag.” L180-L182 . Lastly Participant 5,Arra, “ang self- Fulfillment ko as a teacher alam mo yun meron silang mga realization sa buhay niya Kasi nga more on pagpapakatao eh, so dahil malalim siya minsan ang mga bata Narerealize nila pag ka halimbawa nag discuss kami sa katapatan , yun yung isang Topic namin ngayong fourth quarter so hindi lang sa mga mababaw na paraan na Narealize nila, so pagdating sa bahay na aadopt nila yun tapos yun nga sinasabuhay Nilas so kapag nababalitaan ko yun masaya naman siya sa feeling.” L62-L67.

Co et al. (2021) revealed the commitment and passion to the sworn duty of out-of-the-field teachers to embrace the challenges in their teaching profession. They perceive obstacles as opportunities for the professional growth of teachers, which not only secures their capacities but also protects the public, employers, and, most importantly, students (Bugwak, 2021). In addition, the study of Torcino and Villocino (2023) revealed that out-of-the-field teachers are also learning from the subject taught. Their experiences inspire them to become better teachers by turning their struggles into an opportunities to grow, and this optimism that they have helps them to discover their full potential and started to love, appreciate and see the beauty of subject they are teaching.

For Category 3, Depth in the Subject Matter. The participants revealed that teaching outside their specialization broadens their knowledge. Their continuous learning of the subject allowed them to comprehend the subject matter more deeply—not just its content, but also the subject itself.

As stated Participant 1, Kristian, “Mas lumalawak kasi ano Bicolano kasi ako sa lugar ko dati pag nag tuturo ako ng araling panlipunan kaya learning experience sakín yung pagtuturo ng Filipino subject para mas nagiging matatas ka sa pagsasalita ng tagalog” L68-L74. Additionally Participant 2, JP, “nag kakaroon din ako ng engagement with the subject itself kung baga hindi lang ako naktututok sa kanya sa general lang kung baga natutunan ko din siya eh lumalawak lumalalim.” L64-L66 . Furthermore, Participant 3 Macky, “ nung andun na ako sa actual field dun ko na realize kung gaano siya ka hirap ,siyempre ahm mapeh ahm marunong ka sa talent yung pagkanta pag sayaw , YUn yung realization na kapag MAPEh di lang siya ganun kadali tulad ng sinasabi ng ibang major or courses.” L65-L68

Category 4, maximizing teachers' continued learning. The participants revealed their eagerness to continue their professional growth for they are aware of their weaknesses and strengths as teachers teaching outside their specialization. They seek guidance from the school administration, to attend seminars, trainings, and workshops that will guide them in the subject content and appropriate teaching strategies that they can apply in their teaching. As stated by

Participant 1, Kristian, “sana manlang isang beses sa isang taon mapadala ka sa isang pag sasanay alam mo yun iba parin na may natutunan ka with Filipino teacher na pwede mong ma transfer yung knowledge na yun sa classroom na nakukuha lang i think pag may in service training na minsan very limited lang yung oras like one topic tapos ano mas maganda sana kung medyo mahaba yung training or workshop like 5 days para mas madami yung ma accumulate mong knowledge na pwede mong ma impart sa classroom.” L53-L59. Also Participant 2, JP, “pag bibigay din ng pagbibigay ng instructional material saka training para mas guided din yung mga non major na nagtuturo nun lalo na kung di mo siya porte di mo siya major.” L80-L82. In addition Participant 3 Macky, “mag offer sila mga ano program or mga session na kung saan tutulungan nila yung mga teacher na nagtuturo na hindi naman major nila” L95-L96. Lastly Participant 4 , Christian, “magkaroon ng content training , yun yung number one eh ,If the teacher have no background knowledge in teaching MAPEh it is important na magkaroon ng teaching expertise, seminar para sila din” L197-L199.

In the issue of continuous assignment of teachers outside their specialization, Bugwak (2021), suggests that the issue can be solved by looking at its root cause in hiring teachers which is the responsibility of the school administration. Employing enough numbers of teachers in each specific field as well as hiring qualified teachers by assigning them to teach subjects in line with their learning expertise. Their wide range of knowledge on what they teach will lead to more effective and efficient teaching. Additionally, attending seminars and workshops is the course of action for the out-of-the-field teachers to continue their professional development.

Structural Description

According to Moustakas (1994), structural descriptions are used to understand the essence of a certain phenomenon through qualitative analysis. The experiences of secondary out-of-the-field social science teachers are varied and complicated, influenced by various factors such as time, space, causality, materiality, relationship to others and self, and bodily factors, all of which affect their resilience.

Time

Moustakas (1994) stated that time, examines the past, present, and future to understand the experiences of individuals in the phenomenon. In this research, the structural description focuses on how the participants manage their time to be ready for the classes and their challenges in the content knowledge lead them to put extra time to read and study the lesson. A participant stated that “Kung бага sa isang teacher na major mo yung tinuturo mo parang nag rereview ka nalang sa klase. Sa part ko kailangan ko talagang aralin kung бага para tama yung ma dedeliver ko sa mga bata.”L33-L35. They also learned from past experiences to become more productive for managing their time properly, for instance, one participant stated that “Ang ginagawa ko kasi ngayon ahead of time nag rerecord na ako, hindi ko na pinapaabot yung pag tapos ng exam dun na ko nag rerecord. Dun kasi ako na ano, dun ako na, siguro yun yung pagkakamali ko, nung unang taon ko, after ng exam dun lang ako nag checheck ng notebook, dun lang ako nag rerecord, tambak talagang sobrang dami. Pero ngayon kasi ginagawa ko kunwari after mag turo ng music eh lahat ng notebook nila checheckan ko, maglalaan ako ng isang araw na mag checheck lang kami ng activity tapos i che-check namin yun, kasi fout times a week naman yung MAPEh, so yung strategy ko na yun, pag tapos namin sa music check kami lahat , tapos nun arts na ganun.”L104-L112.

Space

This is a narrative of a person's actual experiences, including the environment in which they encountered the phenomenon (Moustakas, 1994). This social science out-of-the-field teacher faces challenges in their physical and social environments due lack of content knowledge and unfamiliarity with the new environment. However, they show confidence in accepting the challenge of teaching outside of their expertise. A participant said that “ready naman na ko ahm na makapgturo ako ng ibang subject and yun nga yun na nillook forward ko ni reready ko na yung sarili ko . Yung nga pagpasok ko ng Dona nnung ininterview ako sabi nila “willing ka bang magturo ng ibang subject?” sabi ko opo kahit ano pong subject wag lang math” L4-L8.. Additionally, they remain committed to becoming an effective teacher an example of that is the statement of one participant, “Okay naman sila kasi kahit hindi naman natin porte gusto parin natin ideliver na mas maiintindihan nila, so ako pinag aaralan ko para may progress din yung mga bata dun sa subject area na yun kahit ah, hindi ko siya ah porte” L15-L16.

Casuality

According to Moustakas (1994), casuality describes how certain factors have influenced a person's live experiences on the phenomenon. While topic specialization is mandatory for secondary teachers, there are situations where teachers are assigned to teach subjects outside of their areas of expertise because they are not well-versed in the material and find it difficult to instruct. As stated by a participant “una nahihirapan ako na I deliver sa bata as is yung topic, yung content kasi kailangan ko siyang tawag dito kailangan ko siyang pababawin”. L43-L44. However, they are determined to overcome these and continue to give quality education to the learners, a participant said that “ngayon kasi na mamanager ko na mag integrate ng ibat ibang activities, mag integrate ng ibat ibang ah tawag dito methodology sa pagtuturo ahmm kunwari mag papagawa ka ng mga collaborative work ,performance based assesment, may mga ganun “ L43-L46. Additionally this challenge in their teaching career helps them to grow as stated by a participant “ i do believe na nag grogrow ka dun sa outside of your comfort zone kasi pag andun ka lang sa nakasanayan mo ng ilang years ahm hindi ka ganun nag grogrow kasi nga hind mo ganun na experience or naranasna yung ibang area na marami pang opportunities na ma provide sayo”L84-L87.

Materiality

Discussing materiality relates to explaining how the material elements are integral to the experiences of a individual (Moustakas, 1994). In the study, the secondary out-of-the -field teachers struggle with the content and unfamiliarity in the new environment. As stated by the participant, “hindi ko kasi kabisado pa hindi ko kasi gamay yung techniques and strategies how would they like for example Music, Arts, Music and Health and daming components”L27-L29 .Participants become resourceful, it revealed their effort to look for different learning materials that they could use to deliver the lesson properly to the student. A participant said “ang ginawa ko talaga nanuod ako ng mga lectures ng youtube, malaking tulong ng youtube kasi na si- simplify nila yung mga information saka tinuturo at the same time meron na silang format kung paano siya ituturo , yung flow ,so malaking tulong din yun. Tapos basa talaga basa basa basa , ano ba yung mga dapat ko pang eh ituro and yung module din na binigay ng division mas simple mas mabilis ko siyang naiintidihan”L113-L118 . Despite of this difficulties they often find ways to carry on and make the best of what they have.

Bodily concern

According to Moustakas (1994), bodily concern focuses on understanding movements, gestures, expressions, and physiological states that shape individuals' experiences and perceptions. The participants' challenges never become a hindrance for them to have a positive outlook in teaching. A participant stated “I ne-enjoy ko actually kasi kapag hindi ko siya ineenjoy hindi ko talaga siya magugustuhan baka hindi ako magtagal at magreklamo ako sa department head ko diba na lipat na ko sa iba or bumalik na ko sa Araling Panlipunan. So enenjoy ko siya ah” L65-67. They express their excitement for the new experiences “kumbaga parang ang dami mga bagay, yung sa boys scout, yung sa girls scout ah tawag kung baga may mga coordinatorship din na ganun so tawag dun yun yung mga bagay na na eexcite akong gawin” L145-L148. Furthermore, the majority of the participants revealed their sense of surprise and fulfillment as they witnessing the success of their student, the participant stated “yung di ko enexpect na parang nagchachampion yung hawak ko sa MAPEH kasi syempre hindi ako more on talaga eh. I mean first of all hindi talaga align yung knowledge ko sa MAPEh pero since napag aaralan naman siya at natutuwa ako sa mga output ng mga bata and feedback” L55-L57 other participant emphasized “Eh siyempre diba , teaching is a very emotional job, its means that pag ikaw nakita mong mababa yung scores nila , pati ikaw malulungkot ka, pero pag nikita mong masaya sila kasi mataas scores nila, pati ikaw masaya ka, ganun yung nang yayari”L35-L37.

Relationship to self and others

Lastly, this aspect addresses interpersonal and intrapersonal relations.

Researchers investigate people's relationships with others, including family, friends, colleagues, and larger social networks, as well as their interactions with themselves (Moustakas, 1994). When it comes to the participants' relationship to others and themselves, it was evident that they exhibited a good relationship with themselves and others. In this study the participants receive good feedback from their head department. As one of the participant said “base on sa sinasabi ng head ko sa MAPEh, so far natutuwa naman siya , minsan nga sinasabi nila na mag mapeh na lang daw ako all throughout wag na daw akong bumalik ng AP kasi nga natutuwa sila sa way ng teaching ko na parang kakaiba na hindi nila nakita before sa ibang MAPEh teacher.”L50-L53 . Additionally the participants stated that the support of their colleagues was essential in guiding them to teach outside of their field “meron kaming tinatawag na team teaching, magtutulongan kami ng meron kasi kaming coordinator dun, siya lang ang nag iisang MAPEh major dun the rest ng ahat ng teacher dun ibang major na, Hindi madami kami as in isa lang talaga yung original na MAPEh, then the rest hugot nalang “L89-L92. In this experiences on of the participant stated the importance of knowing themselves as a way of overcoming the challenges in teaching in out of the field, “Naniniwala ako kapag focus ka sa ginagawa mo,mas productive ka saka when you know yourself very well , and it will become successful in your endeavors ,kasi kung di mo kilala sarili mo ay hindi mo paniniwalaan na kaya mong gawin yung isang bagay. So kilalanin mo sarili mo para malaman” L158-L162.

Essence

From the structural and textural descriptions, the Researcher then writes a composite description that presents the “essence” of the phenomenon, called the essential, invariant structure (or essence). Primarily this passage focuses on the common experiences of the participants. (Moustakas, 1994). One of the specific cases of the participants showed their passion and commitment to teaching to accept the challenge of teaching outside their specialization. Despite a lack of content knowledge and unfamiliarity, they continue to express their admirable love for teaching and for the student by their endless effort to give quality learning to the students. The participants exert extra time and effort to study the subject by looking for any learning materials that can help them to understand the lesson and they use various teaching strategies that engage the students to give meaningful learning. Additionally, it showed the significance of a good working environment, the good leadership of the head department, and the support of the colleagues with the participants helps them to continue teaching despite the challenges.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

An insufficient number of teachers can lead to out-of-the-field teaching and despite the difficulty of mastering the subject matter and adapting to unfamiliar aspects of their new teaching environment, social science teachers remain committed to effective teaching and learning by innovating interactive activities and interdisciplinary teaching.

To overcome the challenges of teaching outside their specialization, social science out-of-the-field teachers employ various coping strategies being prepared, receptive, and resourceful. Additionally, a good working relationship with colleagues is important for encouraging social science out-of-the-field teachers, giving constructive criticism, exchanging ideas on subject content and instructional techniques, and fostering collaborative teaching.

Social science out-of-the-field teachers continue to be devoted to their sworn duty as educators; despite challenges, they take pride in their profession and find fulfillment in seeing their students succeed. Teaching outside their specialization creates continuous learning for social science teachers, they exhibit a keen enthusiasm for professional development and strive to expand their understanding of the subject matter

This qualitative study provided a descriptive understanding of the experiences of secondary out-of-the-field social science teachers,

suggests that:

For Students. They may interact and engage in the classroom even though their subject is taught by an out-of-field teacher. They may respect the effort put forth by their teachers, who never stop trying their hardest to ensure that they have a worthwhile educational experience.

For Out-of-the-field Teachers. The study suggests the need for training and workshops to support out-of-the-field teachers in their teaching practices. Investigating the impact of various teacher training programs may reveal how teachers are committed and equipped to demonstrate effective teaching to the students.

For the Department Head. The study suggests their supervision to their out-of-field teachers. Their leadership can inspire them by giving them the right orientation on what to expect when teaching outside of their area of expertise and by providing feedback on their strengths and weaknesses, encouraging them to work even harder to become effective teachers.

For School Head. He may develop well-thought-out strategies and programs specifically tailored to out-of-field teachers' needs and issues by providing them opportunities to learn more and to grow professionally which can empower these teachers to enhance their subject knowledge, improve their teaching practices, and ultimately contribute to better student outcomes

For The Department of Education. The study suggests investigating the real reason for out-of-the-field teaching and making policies that prevent or even lessen out-of-the-field teaching in the country's education system.

For Future Researchers. This area may focus on understanding the pedagogical teaching strategies of out-of-the-field teachers; this could include identifying their teaching practices and how they utilize them. Considering that out-of-the-field teachers struggle with content knowledge, it would be beneficial to study the effectiveness of out-of-the-field teachers in student learning. Delving into the effectiveness of out-of-the-field teachers, educational researchers can gain valuable insights into the dynamics of teaching outside one's specialization and its implications for student achievement.

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